

careables.org

D2.2

Co-Creation

Catalog

incl. Open Source Healthcare Solutions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Careables.org is an online platform serving as a central hub for sharing knowledge for reproduction and self-creation of customized healthcare solutions. It encompasses a repository for the storage of open hardware projects' technical documentation and it shall represent an environment where individuals with particular needs, caregivers, healthcare professionals, makers, and designers, work collaboratively online to create custom-made healthcare solutions – careables.

One of the core objectives of the project Careables is the co-creation of new solutions. This document is a collection of solutions created to date in different co-design formats and processes at Opendot/TOG in Milan, Waag in Amsterdam, and at FabLab Berlin. All solutions featured in this catalog, and many more, are documented on welder.app/careables. Until now the repository contains more than one hundred entries.

By developing open source hardware solutions in interdisciplinary teams involving users, designers, technicians, and healthcare professionals careables.org provides recipes/instructions on how these open solutions can be replicated with digital fabrication technologies in fabrication laboratories, in maker- and hackerspaces. Many of the solutions created rely on the use of 3D printers and laser cutters, others involve welding, soldering electronic components, working with fabric, or using a CNC mill.

Additionally, to encouraging individuals to reproduce open solutions, we found that workshops can be a suitable format. By organizing as a group of people who are for example interested in building Open Lights for wheelchairs, a local FabLab can provide the space and the machines needed to make the event a success. Very importantly, the produced solutions are not the sole outcome of such a workshop. The experience of building something together, sharing skills, knowledge, and the potential for emphatic understanding are also highly valued by the participants.

In some cases the developments are one-off solutions that are perfectly tailored to a specific need. The documentation of these solutions focuses on the process of the creation, to share lessons learned and also to inspire other potential users, their friends or relatives to go on a similar journey.

During the development process, the focus lays on the user need. These needs can be perceived as very pressing, like in the development of a tricycle for a user who grew up using a bicycle and was dreaming of the independence and fun associated with riding a bicycle. While the production involved modifying a second-hand bicycle the story and the accompanying video of the successful build might inspire many others to actively change their environment and be

encouraged to voice their wishes.

Other factors within the development process, of course, include the feasibility of prototyping the solution, where resources such as required additional funding, potentially missing special knowledge by the team members, time constraints and other aspects can lead to very different possible development paths. We structured the pathways by looking at different motivational motors, possible departure points in a development process.

Sometimes the user need starts from a very clear idea, for example, a pen producing tactile traces, that cure immediately so that they can provide tactile feedback while writing conventionally. In this way, blind children could write on normal paper and seeing children could share this medium. While the idea is very elaborate, it is also very specific and therefore requires a chemical fast-curing ink, which to our knowledge does not exist yet. Creating an atmosphere of creation that allows for pivots is very important from our understanding because the possible solution is of course very dependent on the skills and special knowledge within the development team (Team Skills), as well as financial/material/tooling resources and the time frame available mentioned earlier.

A further motivational motor is the experience of healthcare professionals who identify the need for certain therapeutic needs. These solutions can also aim for user groups who are not (yet) able to express themselves as in the example of toys for children with severe neurological disorders, where practicing hand-eye coordination can be encouraged by haptic games.

A yet under-explored forth motivational motor could mainly stem from current technological developments, such as micro-controllers with embedded offline face-recognition technology. For makers, recent tech developments are often of strong motivation. Here the development pathway involves finding adequate application scenarios, in this case possibly Alzheimer's conditions or also low-vision. Furthermore, it seems advisable to systematically identify clusters of pressing problems and the resources needed to create solutions. This could lead to guiding matrices additionally to the user needs of people one is getting in direct contact with.

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List of abbreviations

CAD	Computer Aided Design
FLOSS	Free Libre Open Source Software
OSH	Open Source Hardware

1. Introduction

The main aim of this report to provide a catalog of the open solutions created to date as part of the project **Careables**.

The solutions featured have been created in different sessions and formats, mostly in co-creation of teams composed of patients/users, makers, designers, and healthcare professionals. The open solutions and recipes to reproduce and adapt the pathways described are part of a growing movement of bottom-up development in the health care sector. The goal is not primarily to replace existing commercial solutions, but to identify room for improvement in the daily lives of users, and to figure out smart solutions for the everyday. While the created solutions are of importance, the individual development processes and group experiences also provide valuable learning opportunities for all participants with respect to group dynamics, social interaction, technical skills, and feasibility constrain.

OBJECTIVE & MOTIVATIONAL MOTORS

Goal of this catalog is to provide an alternative entry point to explore the open solutions documented on our internet platform, to assemble solutions and attempts, and to provide additional background information with a strong focus on the solutions created, as well as the challenges and pitfalls of creating documentations while learning new skills and trying to finish a great prototype.

Additionally to the creation and documentation of specific solutions, we want to highlight the experience and the benefits of the development journey. Here we identified three main motivational motors or starting points, which are the base for the clustering of the solutions created so far. We identified user needs, team skills, and professional healthcare needs as viewpoints being all valid ways of starting development. Often these different viewpoints are intertwined, but this report also wants to stress the specific importance of the team skills involved in the development process.

To provide a specific example: *In one of our formats, the Open Health HACKademy #1, our lead user of one of the projects, a deaf person, was imagining an owl - inspired by a Harry Potter character- to seamlessly communicate with the hearing community as well as to be an icebreaker or communication starter. The team decided it would be worthy to prototype an implementation of an owl and the initial investigation showed, that the benefits in speed and accuracy of using a commercial cloud-based speech-to-text and a text-to-speech solution would*

outweigh the privacy-concerns as well as the need for an internet connection. A smartphone was imagined as an interface to send chat-messages to the owl, reading out the messages as well as, transcribing the answers given by the hearing person, to be sent back to the phone. Having the owl act as a Bluetooth speaker with a microphone seemed like a great technical solution, but the engineers involved in the project said they specifically had experience in the Python programming language as well as in Raspberry Pi development. Possibly in further development steps, there will be yet another solution process.

Important learning of the processes conducted is to leave room for these changes in planning. Participants might be curious in learning basic programming during the development process, providing a steep learning experience for the members of the team.

Motivational Motors of Co-Designing Open Solutions

Co-Design processes can be driven by different motivational motors: While user needs are a core factor in the development of open solutions, the skills of the team also shape the solutions created. While the team might agree that a certain approach would be preferable, skills and resources involved lead to very different solutions created. A third approach is where health care professional identify a therapeutic need and team up with designers, makers and technologists.

Figure 1: Motivational Motors

2. Outlook

Parametric Solutions and FLOSS tool-chains

A special point of interest is the general question of software toolchains for the creation of open source hardware. Here the advice is to use FLOSS software for the creation, as this is the best way to ensure unrestrained access for adaptation and for the continuation of development¹. This becomes especially relevant in the creation of so-called parametric solutions:

Ideally, the CAD models created during the development are easily modifiable to other users aiming to reproduce and adapt the solutions.

In a parametric solution created by PillStorage Fits All (p. 32) the Designer mentions the tricks necessary for user modification of parameters in the CAD Software Fusion 360 and to combine it with an Excel sheet for changing parameters.

The next step within Careables is to finalize a web interface prototype for the parametric opens source CAD solution OpenSCAD to have the adaptation on the user side as seamless as possible. Another challenge is to create easy toolchains for designers and makers to use FLOSS software for the creation and documentation of their OSH solutions.

1 Compare Joshua Pearce "5 keys to building open hardware"
<https://opensource.com/article/18/2/5-steps-creating-successful-open-hardware>

3. Co-creation Catalog of Open Solutions

Adjustable Shopping Trolley - The City Aid

Adjustable Shopping Trolley - THE CITY aid

5

THE CITY AID Trolley is meant to give an practical comfort in shopping. [more](#)

Healthcare

An adjustable shopping bag for people with movement restrains. The goal of this project to remain independent even with mobility issues. It is meant to make it easier to keep doing groceries independently.

Core Team of **3**

Tools:
No specialized tools needed.

Table 1: Adjustable Shopping Trolley - The City Aid

Camping Lift for Wheelchair Users

[camping lift for wheelchair users](#)

0

To design a device to get safely from the ground into your wheelchair. [more](#)

Making camping in a tent possible for wheelchair users: Getting from the ground into your wheelchair is always difficult, especially when you and your partner are getting older. We want to design a device, "the camping lift for wheelchair users", that makes it possible to get safely from the ground into your wheelchair without any distress to the partner.

Core Team of **4**

Tools:

Laser cutter
Woodworking tools

Table 2: Camping Lift for Wheelchair Users

CapraSTICK

CapraSTICK

1

create an intuitive control for an electronic wheelchair

[. more](#)

3d Printing

Mobility

Self Care

CapraSTICK is a wheelchair joystick that is ergonomic and designed for safe use. This involves uniquely assigning all keys and functions so that operator errors can be avoided. Besides, the joystick is better in the hand and can be used ambidextrous and variable.

Core Team of **5**

Tools:

3D Printer
Electronics

Table 3: CapraSTICK

Chill Pill

The Chill Pill device is specifically designed to help aid those who suffer from anxiety and stress disorders in a fast and effective way.

Core Team of 6

Tools:
3D printer
Electronics

Table 4: Chill Pill

Customizable Wrist Brace

Customizable Wrist Brace

📶 4

A wrist brace that can be pre-set at with a personalized tension for easy securement. [more](#)

A wrist brace that allows the user to preset the tension of individual parts of the brace. This allows for the user to put the brace on more easily as they only have to tighten the preset tab rather than each strip.

Core Team of **1**

Tools:
Laser cutter

Table 5: Customizable Wrist Brace

Da-vi-do

da-vi-do

2

Da-vi-do is a musical instrument specifically adapted to kids with motor disability. [more](#)

Arduino Healthcare Learning/communication

The instrument is custom-made for the special needs of Davide. He has infantile cerebral palsy and a motor disability which causes him a lack of precision, delayed and unrepeatable movements and hand actions with non-identical power.

Core Team of 5

Tools:

- 3D printer
- Laser cutter
- Electronics

Table 6: Da-vi-do

Drifter Car - A Students Project

Drifter Car- A Students Project

7

Drifter Car is an electrical car, fitted to the needs of a child with spastic quadriplegia. [more](#)

4 Wheeled Robots

Arduino

Fun/leisure

Laser Cutting

Drifter car aims to create a new game for every child, that can be a functional and emotional help for those who suffer from spastic quadriplegia or any other motor disease.

Core Team of **5**

Tools:

- 3D printer
- Laser cutter
- Electronics

Table 7: Drifter Car - A Students Project

Easy Cut

easy cut

Easy cut is a chopping board designed to solve one-handed person in cutting food. [more](#)

Laser Cutting

Single-hand disabled people have a lot of inconvenience in cutting food, for example when vegetables are rolling away. The “easy cut” chopping board aims to solve this kind of problem. Most of its parts are made with laser cutting, so others can reproduce and improve it.

Core Team of **6**

Tools:
Laser cutter

Table 8: Easy Cut

EVS
Eye Vibration Sensor

The device allows the fencer, through different intensities of vibration, to understand the distance between him and his opponent. The project started with the desire to make fencing more dynamic and simple for blind people.

EVS eye vibration sensor

Distance support for blind fencing team. [more](#)

- 3d Printing
- Arduino
- Computer Vision
- Haptic Feedback
- Human-robot Interaction

Core Team of 4

Tools:
3D printer
Electronics

Table 9: EVS - Eye Vibration Sensor

Eyetractive

EyeTracktive

6

Bringing affordable eye tracking to google cardboard.
[more](#)

Learning/communication

Therapy

A project to better understand and work with Lazy Eye. We wanted to reduce the cost of eye-tracking by 10X, to make it accessible to 72% of the world earning less than \$10 a day.

A solution that works with second-generation Google Cardboards, simply replacing its central insert. Simple. Affordable. Ecologically sound.

The core uses nothing more than cardboard, which can be cut by laser, or by hand. Just fold it up and insert it.

Core Team of 6

Tools:

Laser cutter
Electronics

Table 10: Eyetractive

Finger Eyes for Blind Reading

FINGER EYES for BLIND READING

Infrared sensors read lines and vibration motors give haptic feedback at the fingers. [more](#)

A tool to sense what you wrote on paper, without eyesight! Juli, a twelve-year-old blind girl is the initiator and lead user of this project. She can write but never read it afterward. She wants to be able to use a regular notebook (not a TACT Sketchpad e.g.). We found out that at least 3 fingers are necessary for recognizing structures by touch. The tool should look cool, normal. Our current Prototype uses Infrared sensors to recognize black lines and vibration motors to give haptic feedback at the fingertips.

Core Team of **4**

Tools:
3D printer
Electronics

Table 11: Finger Eyes for Blind Reading

Glifo – Writing Tool

Glifo - writing tool

Glifo is a writing support. It's light, washable and adjustable for any hand measures!. [more](#)

3d Printing

Daily Living

Fun/leisure

Learning/communication

Glifo is a writing support tool used to help children with motor difficulties to draw and write independently. It was born from the co-design between Opendot fablab, TOG, Sara Monacchi, Andrea Pelino, Luca Toscano, therapists with kinesiological skills and families of children with disabilities.

Core Team of **7**

Tools:
3D printer

Table 12: Glifo – Writing Tool

Gudret

A bracelet that vibrates to reduce hand tremors in Parkinson's patients. The vibration introduces white noise which distracts the brain from hand tremors.

Gudret

📶 2

We're building a device for Parkinson's patients that would help reduce hand tremors. [more](#)

Arduino

Embedded Software

Haptic Feedback

Core Team of **4**

Tools:
Electronics

Table 13: Gudret

Helpers Helper

Helpers Helper

5

Practicing g-tube replacement procedures with a dummy. [more](#)

Self Care

Many people with severe and/or progressive illnesses are provided with a PEG probe, a gastrostomy tube (also called a G-tube) or a button in the course of their lives to support their diet. The button and the G-tube can be exchanged quickly and easily at home without medical assistance if it's broken or something does not work. The instruction on the process of exchanging the G-tube is usually only carried out theoretically. With the Helpers Helper dummy we want to create a remedy. You can practice with it at any time, which gives you a feeling for the change and thus helps to reduce your fears.

Core Team of **4**

Tools:

3D printer
Silicone molding

Table 14: Helpers Helper

Hyperactive Stool

Hyperactive Stool

3

Stool for hyperactive children suffering from autism.
[more](#)

- Cnc Milling
- Daily Living
- Mobility
- Self Care
- Therapy

An unstable seat to increase the attention of hyperactive children in class. The user can move freely. Blue color has been chosen to coat the seat, which conveys a sense of calmness and well-being to the mind.

Core Team of **8**

Tools:
CNC milling

Table 15: Hyperactive Stool

Intelligent Lights for Light Sensitivity and Night Blindness

Intelligent Lights for Light Sensitivity and Night Bli... 3

A dimmable light in the form of a torch and an intelligent lighting system for the home. [more](#)

A portable, dimmable flashlight with a texture for easier grip. The lamp allows for both direct, and ambient lighting. Serving as a hotspot in the apartment the light is also controlling the light fixtures, thereby providing an alternative to the manual operation of the light switches.

Core Team of **2**

Tools:
Electronics

Table 16: Intelligent Lights for Light Sensitivity and Night Blindness

Interdental Brushes Holder

interdental brushes holder

a holder for your interdental brushes to optimize hygiene and order. [more](#)

A holder for inter-dental brushes to optimize hygiene and order. The project started with the need for a system to store different sizes of inter-dental brushes.

The user needs different sizes of brushes to clean between the teeth. He experienced difficulties in having an order to store the different sizes of brushes and his wish was to have a simple system to keep the different sizes apart.

Core Team of **2**

Tools:
3D printer

Table 17: Interdental Brushes Holder

LIL

Lil

8

Montessorian panels for children with complex neurological conditions . [more](#)

3d Printing

Arduino

Laser Cutting

5 different interactive panels to help fine and global mobility of the upper part of the body of children with complex neurological conditions.

Flower: When you grab the stem of the flower and pull it toward you, the petals open radially.

Window: When you open the window you see a monkey and a pig and can listen their sound.

Rocket: When you push the rocket upwards the lights turn on.

Rudder: When the ship's wheel is turned, the sea will follow.

Light bulbs: When you spin the light bulbs they will gradually turn the light on.

Core Team of **5**

Tools:

Laser cutter
Electronics

Table 18: LIL

Lupo White Cane Tip

Lupo white cane tip

7

it's a custom made, 3D printed white cane tip. [more](#)

"Lupo" is a very active visually impaired person. He walks a lot around Milan by himself, and he remembers a lot of streets by heart. He is using a rolling tip for his white cane, but he wasn't satisfied with the one he could buy.

Core Team of **4**

Tools:
3D printer

Table 19: Lupo White Cane Tip

Odyschrift Connect Four

The physical version of the game Connect 4 is adapted for a dyskinetic child, so she can play it with her peers, without interruptions due to the restrictions of the child.

Odyschrift Connect Four

11

Enabling people with motor disabilities to play Connect Four with only an 'Ody' joystick. [more](#)

Fun/leisure

Core Team of **4**

Tools:
Laser cutter
Electronics

Table 20: Odyschrift Connect Four

Open Lights

OPEN LIGHTS

📶 10

OPEN LIGHTS for wheelchairs can be built with most common DIY technologies. . [more](#)

We developed OPEN LIGHTS for wheelchairs that can be built with the most common DIY technologies. The components can be ordered online and produced with 3D printers and laser cutters. You can pick your favourite colours and shapes and even program the lighting modes yourself!

Core Team of **4**

Tools:

- 3D printer
- Laser cutter
- Electronics

Table 21: Open°Lights

Open Trailer

Open Trailer

3

Can be used as a shopping aid or for the pleasure of a riding companion. [more](#)

Daily Living

Fun/leisure

Mobility

Whether as a shopping aid or for the pleasure of a riding companion, the trailer has proven to be a successful add-on for electric wheelchairs users. You can now build it yourself with materials costing less than 100 EUR. The components are mainly CNC-milled (one of the standard DIY technologies). The 3D file is customizable for different wheelchair models and in different styles.

Core Team of 7

Tools:

CNC Machine
Handtools

Table 22: Open°Trailer

O_Zwo

O_Zwo

4

Glasses for oxygen patients. The Glasses fits for most standard oxygen tubes. [more](#)

- 3d Printers
- Daily Living
- Healthcare
- Mobility
- Rehabilitation

The glasses help people with the need of additional oxygen to give better comfort in daily life.

The glasses can be used for the most common standard oxygen tubes. The tube is pressed into a groove in the glasses and can so easily be removed and replaced.

The glasses you see in the pictures is made by the Formlabs 3D-printer.

Core Team of 1

Tools:
SLA 3D printer

Table 23: O_Zwo

PillStorage Fits All

PillStorage Fits All

5

A parametric pillbox, divided in the days of the week.
[more](#)

Daily Living

Self Care

The project contains a storage unit for pills. There is a box present for each day of the week containing 3 different slots where the pill is stored. The seven daily pillboxes are stored in a larger unit covering the week.

The origin of the case comes from a person dealing with epilepsy.

Core Team of **2**

Tools:

3D printer

Laser cutter

Table 24: PillStorage Fits All

Pimping my Cane

Pimping my Cane

As visually impaired person, I can always see the other participants in the traffic hustle. So, I decided to enhance my own visibility. As I always... [more](#)

A revised version of the classic white cane that is used by blind or visually impaired people to spot objects in the path of its uses. The added feature is that it glows in the dark to guarantee visibility in the darker urban surrounding.

Core Team of **3**

Tools:

3D printer
Electronics

Table 25: Pimping my Cane

PVC Foot

PVC-foot

📶 19

Lightweight foot for the self-adjustable prosthesis.
[more](#)

PVC-foot is a lightweight and low-cost prosthesis made from recycled materials, mainly from PVC pipe and rubber tires. PVC-Foot aims to empower the people to produce their prostheses by spreading a production manual for a self-adjustable and low-cost prosthesis which can be made with local materials and minimal knowledge on manufacturing.

Core Team of **5**

Tools:
 Handtools

Table 26: PVC Foot

Quali-Fire

Quali-fire

14

This speculative project aimed to use automated measurement to better understand the cause. [more](#)

Quali-fire was developed to help people with the chronic disease Multiple Sclerosis, by developing a tool that could monitor and visualize signs of inflammation caused by disease activity.

Over the longer term, the ambition was to find the relationships between disease activity and overall health, by looking at the relationship to environmental factors such as sleep management, nutrition, exercise, heat exposure, and stress.

Core Team of 4

Tools:
Electronics

Table 27: Quali-Fire

Removable Mid-Step

Removable Mid-Step 11

We want to redevelop a device to make stair climbing more easy. [more](#)

With this device, people will be able to walk the stairs easier. It is a walking stick with an attached block to reduce the height of a step.

Core Team of **7**

Tools:
Handtools

Table 28: Removable Mid-Step

Removable Mid-Step II

Removable Mid-Step II

The removable Mid-Step is a mobility aid that helps elderly people walk the stairs. [more](#)

The removable Mid-Step is a project in which a personal aid has been created. This aid supports people that have increasing trouble when mounting stairs. It works by offering a mid-step through which every stair step becomes more accessible.

Core Team of **7**

Tools:
Laser cutter
Handtools

Table 29: Removable Mid-Step II

Rollavie Modified Walker

Rollavie modified walker

5

redeveloping the walker to appeal to younger people.
[more](#)

Healthcare

Mobility

This project its main focus is to change the view of existing walkers to make it more fitting to personal taste. When people for whatever reason have to use a walker in their personal life they receive the same looking walker. Age and personal taste are not included in the walker you receive.

Core Team of **4**

Tools:

- Handtools
- CNC milling
- 3D printer

Table 30: Rollavie Modified Walker

ROW-RO

ROW-RO

4

A hand appliance that helps people who are not able to use their hands. . [more](#)

- 3d Printing
- Digital Fabrication
- Healthcare
- Laser Cutting
- Low-cost Fabrication

Row-Ro is a custom made half-open glove that is specifically designed for Rosina, a thirty-one years old girl who has incomplete tetraplegia which does not permit her to close her fingers, thus making it impossible to grab objects.

She is currently using a gym object that allows her to continue her passion for rowing but that causes her pain and does not offer a natural grip.

The product consists of a partially open glove in neoprene with rigid supports in PLA, 3d printing, which offer support to the wrist involving the thumb and part of the palm below the little finger.

Core Team of 4

Tools:

- Handtools
- 3D printer

Table 31: ROW-RO

Sen-C Music Box

Sen-C Music Box

2

Sen-C is a toy specifically made for children (age 4-7) with visual impairments. . [more](#)

Arduino

Fun/leisure

Laser Cutting

Sen-c is a toy specifically made for children with visual impairments. The children can play alone or with any other friends. We empower children by allowing them to feel and to learn the shape of different animals through their tactile and auditory senses. This is made possible with a music box- created by laser cutting plywood- and the use of Arduino with NFC tags. Our biggest inspiration was the researches we've done when first starting with this project as they have stated that visually impaired children have to spend the rest of their life in blindness, which heavily impacts their educational opportunities, employment and earning potential.

Core Team of **6**

Tools:

Laser cutter
Electronics

Table 32: Sen-C Music Box

Smart Toys

Smart Toys

📶 20

smart toys for kids to exercise at home. [more](#)

A custom toy for kids age 8-12 to exercise at home. The toy is a physical exercise remote control for a robot that drives around. By using the hand crank one can control the robot and do one's exercises at the same time!

Core Team of **4**

Tools:

- Laser cutter
- 3D printer
- Electronics

Table 33: Smart Toys

Squeeze-a-Ring

Squeeze-a-ring

📶 17

Squeeze-a-ring is a knitted, ring-shaped sensor to measure pain in a clinical environment. [more](#)

So far, we have made a knitted squeeze sensor, we did some initial interface design (picture below), and connected the sensor to a laptop through an Arduino to visualize sensor pressure (picture above). Initially, we conceptualized our solution as a stress ball, and we frumpled the knitted sensor in a knitted sleeve. It turned out the sensor was not reliable enough in this way and we are now experimenting with a custom-made silicone spindle that will allow the sensor to bounce back to its initial shape. This spindle was cast in a 3D printed mold.

Core Team of
11

Tools:
Knitting needles
Electronics
3D printer

Table 34: Squeeze-a-Ring

Stomanoir New

<p>Stomanoir new 📡 9</p> <p>Support Ostomates in their hygiene care by developing sanitary solutions to personal i. more</p> <p>Careware Mobility</p>	<p>It is quite a simple product. It is no more than a customizable cap that one can use to seal a used stoma pouch enabling air-tightness so that unpleasant odors cannot escape. This creates better opportunities for comfortably disposing of used bags in public places.</p>	
	<p>Core Team of 3</p>	<p>Tools: Laser cutter Silicone</p>

Table 35: Stomanoir New

SunnyGlass

What if you could just wear glasses to be out in the sun? These light therapy glasses aim to conquer depression and signs of sadness with a light source imitating daylight.

SunnyGlass

8

Light Therapy Solution . [more](#)

3d Printing

Careware

Daily Living

Digital Fabrication

Healthcare

Core Team of **6**

Tools:

3D printer
Electronics

Table 36: SunnyGlass

Svens Special Trike

Svens Special Trike

A recumbent trike conforming to specific needs, with custom brakes, steering, and saddle. [more](#)

Daily Living

Fun/leisure

Mobility

Our team modified a recumbent trike for Sven, to conform to his specific needs.

Sven has spastic tetraplegia. He has most of his fine motor control in his lower body, so most of the trike's systems have to be controlled with his feet, especially the brakes.

The braking system was accomplished with a standard coaster brake with a slight modification of the drive train. The cockpit was customized to be at the ideal height and angle for comfort and stability, and the correct size for Sven's body. The steering system was also modified asymmetrically.

Core Team of **6**

Tools:

Welding
Hand tools

Table 37: Svens Special Trike

T-CUP

T-CUP

A product development for PD people and others, suffering from tremors. . [more](#)

Daily Living

Mobility

The product is an adaptation of a project called "The Gudret Project". In this project, a team worked on a device that could detect tremors and send vibrations back to counter the tremor. For now, there is a device that needs to be tested and if it's working there should be a shell covering the product.

T-CUP: Tremor Controlled User-designed Product. The name is also fitting to the project because one of the interview outcomes is that people with tremors struggle with drinking because of the shaking, everything will fall out of the cup.

Core Team of 1

Tools:
3D printer
Electronics

Table 38: T-CUP

Wheelchair-Ramp for one step

The 3D printed ramp helps to overcome a step in front of a building, a shop, cafe or bar. It is as small as possible, to carry it in a bag when being out and about.

The project aims to support the accessibility for wheelchair users.

3D printed Wheelchair-Ramp for one step

12

This ramps helps to overcome a step in front of a building, a shop, cafe or bar. [more](#)

Outdoor Installations

Core Team of **2**

Tools:

3D printer

Table 39: Wheelchair-Ramp for one step

Wheelchair Simulator

Wheelchair Simulator

3

The project goal is to help operators in the rehabilitation field. [more](#)

- 3d Printing
- Arduino
- Rehabilitation
- Therapy

The product is a Simulator of a Wheelchair joystick. By using an arcade joystick you can move a led pixel on a light trail. There are many levels sorted by difficulty.

This product was made for tetraplegic people and the aim is to evaluate their skills. The intention is also to exercise the precision and strength of the arm. Once the user-built enough confidence with the device the operator decides if the patient can use a real wheelchair.

Core Team of **6**

Tools:

- Laser cutter
- 3D printer
- Electronics

Table 40: Wheelchair Simulator

XYLOVIBE

XYLOVIBE

3

A toy that is used by all kids along the spectrum of hearing impairments whether . [more](#)

A toy that is used by all kids along the spectrum of hearing impairments whether completely impaired or not, and allowing them to feel connected. We will be doing this through a xylophone, which is a toy used by all and is one of the most basic forms to teach young kids "rhythm and sound".

The goal is to integrate Arduino and a vibrating sound system to a xylophone to allow children with different levels of hearing impairment including completely profound deaf to understand music through different vibrations.

Core Team of 4

Tools:

- Laser cutter
- 3D printer
- Electronics

Table 41: XYLOVIBE